

MILESTONE REPORT

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN AND TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF DAQ INTERFACES FOR HIGHLY GRANULAR ELECTROMAGNETIC AND HADRONIC CALORIMETERS

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Abstract:

Prototypes of highly granular calorimeters are also testing grounds for a) DAQ systems that ensure a proper common running of different calorimetric systems and b) readout system that fulfil the tight requirements of future detectors in terms of space. This document reports on the progress of these DAQ systems towards a common system to be tested until Month 36.

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2022

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Executive summary

Highly granular calorimeters at future $e+e-$ colliders will feature up to 100M cells (or even more), and require embedded very-front-end and readout electronics. On the other hand, the corresponding readout system must not compromise the precision of the measurements. This calls for compact readout systems.

We present the state of the art of compact readout cards, handling up to 10,000 cells, that are connected to data concentrator units implementing already the necessary features for full-detector systems. A calorimetric system consists typically of an electromagnetic section and a hadronic section. These have to be integrated into a common readout system. This document reports on the setup of a common system of an electromagnetic and a hadronic calorimeter that recently has been tested in a large-scale beam test at CERN. The compact readout system developed for a silicon tungsten electromagnetic calorimeter (SiW-ECAL) has been part of the common data acquisition system. At the end, we present conceptual ideas to adapt this system to a highly granular calorimeter based on scintillating tiles and silicon-photomultipliers (AHCAL). Further a possible spin-off, the application in the LUXE experiment is sketched at the end of this report.

1. INTRODUCTION

One goal of the AIDAInnova project is to prepare the construction of detectors at future facilities. Calorimeter systems are a crucial component of particle physics detectors, allowing the measurement of both electrically charged and neutral particles. Modern Particle Flow Algorithms (PFA), that optimally combine the information from several sub-detectors in the reconstruction of each particle, require highly granular calorimeters. With an unprecedented number of calorimeter cells of up to 100 million, these detectors pose a significant challenge for the readout systems. Especially for detectors at a future electron-positron collider, with their stringent requirements on precision and hermeticity, the non-instrumented regions should be kept minimal, making the compactness of the components of the readout system very important. The implementation of the readout system has to take into account differences between an electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL), which is smaller, more compact and has a larger channel density, and a hadronic calorimeter (HCAL), which is larger and has a smaller channel density.

The work presented in this milestone report capitalises on base work carried out in the AIDA and AIDA-2020 predecessor projects. The compact readout system presented in this report has been developed for the silicon-tungsten (SiW) ECAL prototype of the CALICE collaboration during AIDA-2020. In the frame of AIDAInnova, the readout system has been further developed and has been tested for the first time in large-scale beam tests. These beam tests comprised the CALICE SiW ECAL and the CALICE AHCAL, an HCAL based on small scintillator tiles individually read out by SiPMs. These tests gave valuable input for adaptations of the compact readout system for the AHCAL, and are a proof-of-principle towards the Deliverable 8.1.

2. A COMPACT READOUT SYSTEM FOR SiW ECAL

Several DAQ systems have been proposed and partially developed in the framework of the detector R&D for future colliders and the FP7 and H2020 programs (EUNET, AIDA, AIDA-2020). Each had a hardware and high-level software component. For the latter, the EUDAQ system [6] has followed a continuous development and is now the reference for many beam test acquisitions. The hardware component, on the other hand, follows the fast evolution of the innovation in electronics and must be redesigned regularly, integrating the knowledge gained on the previous generation.

For the highly granular calorimeters, the implementation described here is the 3rd generation, featuring a higher level of integration, a much more compact design, and improved, built-in monitoring capacities. As such, it can be seen as the first prototype of a DAQ geometrically suitable for Higgs-factories detectors. It is interfaced to a LabWindows graphical interface, which also provides a bridge to the EUDAQ system.

2.1. HARDWARE

The Slab Interface Board (SL-Board) is the sole interface for the ~10,000 channels of a detector layer. In case of the SiW ECAL, the channels are read out by SKIROC2 and SKIROC2a ASICs, of which a detailed description can be found elsewhere [1,2].

The SL-Board is designed to fit the space and mechanical constraints of the SiW ECAL of ILD.

Being an effective prolongation of a layer, the SL-Board has a length between 10 and 42 mm and a width of 180 mm. The design, see Figure 1 (left), allows for the integration of a cooling system for the SiW ECAL [3]. The height of the SL-Board must be contained between 6 and 12 mm in order to accommodate 15 SL-Boards above each other, in an ILD SiW ECAL barrel module. Within a detector system, the SL-Boards are connected to a Control and Readout (CORE) Module through a bus system, so-called CORE Kapton, via a flexible internal kapton layer and a 40-pin connector (see Figure 1 (middle)). For a detailed description of the SL-Board and the compact readout system, the reader is referred to the corresponding AIDA-2020 report [4].

Since the end of AIDA-2020 a version 2 of the SL-Board has been designed and produced and is now in operation.

Figure 1: Left: Version 2 of the SL-Board. Middle: Connection of the SL-Board to a mezzanine card (CORE Daughter) via the CORE Kapton. Right: CORE Module that houses the mezzanine card. Also visible are connectors for the signal exchange used in the common running of the CALICE SiW ECAL and the CALICE AHCAL.

The main features of this new version are outlined in the following:

- The length of the short flat cable leaving the SL-Board has been increased from 40 to 48 mm, which facilitates its connection to the CORE Kapton in the tight environment of a beam test setup;

- The main input plugs have been rearranged across the board to facilitate the connection of the board to, e.g., high voltage and low voltage power supplies;
- The connector for the FTDI USB module is changed and moved. Now it takes less space and is easier to handle;
- A switch permits the encoding of the slot number;
- The SL-Board now features a DAC for ADC calibration of the front-end ASICs. It also permits delivering calibration pulses with a programmable amplitude;
- A flash EEPROM provides permanent information storage of, e.g., the serial number of connected Active Sensor Units (ASUs, the entity of front-end ASICs, PCB and silicon sensors);
- The FPGA produces pulses for the autonomous functional calibration of the two gains available in the ASIC;
- The HV is transmitted to the ASUs via the regular connectors between SL-Board and the ASUs. This avoids long copper sheets for the HV transmission. The ASUs become therefore individual units and the layers get fully modular. On the ASUs themselves the HV is guided to a copper sheet on the bottom of the ASUs. The copper sheet in turn is glued to the silicon sensors.

2.2. SOFTWARE

The acquisition software is written in C language and developed under LabWindows CVI. It pilots the communication through the CORE Kapton or through the FTDI module directly to the SL-Board. It handles the control and readout of a whole detector module consisting of two CORE Kaptons connected to 15 SL-Boards each and up to five ASUs connected in series to each SL-Board. Core functionalities have been available at the end of AIDA-2020. For the recent testbeam, the graphical interface allows for an extended real-time control of the detector performance. Recently available features are:

- Online hit maps and shower profiles that allow for real-time beam and detector tuning, e.g., adaptation of beam rates or thresholds;
- Pedestal measurement and subtraction;
- Charge measurement and histogramming;
- MIP gain correction.

3. COMMON DATA TAKING SIW ECAL + AHCAL

In June 2022, a 2-week combined beam test of the CALICE SiW ECAL and AHCAL could finally take place. A picture of the setup is given in Figure 2. The SiW ECAL included 15 layers, of 1,024 channels each. The AHCAL had 38 layers of 576 channels each.

This section describes the main features of the common running.

Figure 2: Picture of the combined beam test setup of the CALICE SiW ECAL and the CALICE AHCAL in the SPS H2 beam line at CERN, in June 2022.

3.1. COMMON READOUT – TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION

The scheme of the common readout is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Schematic view of the common readout system setup for the common running of the CALICE SiW ECAL and the CALICE AHCAL.

The entire system is synchronised by the Clock and Control Card (CCC), a device that has been developed in the EU-project EUDET [5], treating 3 synchronisation signals. It provides a 40 MHz clock to all systems. Further, it sends an acquisition window within which data can be acquired. It receives the busy signals sent by the systems during their acquisition periods. The logical OR of the signals inhibits the transmission of a new acquisition window. At the end of all busy signals, the next acquisition window can be sent by the CCC. Both systems should see beam data at the same point in time, internally marked with the so-called bunch-crossing ID (BCID). Due to different delays in each system initialisation and possible clock-boundary conditions, the asynchronous beam signal should be seen with a constant offset plus or minus 1 BCID.

Figure 4 shows the difference in bunch crossing IDs for beam signals recorded by the two systems. The spikes at 0 (corrected for the constant offset) demonstrate the stability of the system synchronisation.

Figure 4: Differences of time stamps for beam signals seen by the CALICE SiW ECAL and the CALICE AHCAL for various layers during the beam test at CERN. The dominant spike demonstrates the stability of the synchronisation of the two detectors. The out-of-time spectrum arise from noise, physical delayed events (late contributions), and beam pile-up.

The actual common data acquisition is based on EUDAQ2, the data acquisition system that has been developed in AIDA and AIDA-2020 and is widely used in beam tests in Europe [6]. A command window is interfaced to the readout systems of the two detectors. The detector systems are configured such that they can receive *run-start* and *run-stop* commands from the control window. The data are acquired and pre-processed by individual producers. Each system pre-processed data are sent via TCP sockets to data collectors, writing data to disk and providing an extended online monitoring. The entire scheme put in place for the common SiW ECAL/AHCAL beam test in June 2022 is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Schematic view of the data acquisition scheme used for the common running of the CALICE SiW ECAL and the CALICE AHCAL. The DAQ is based in EUDAQ. The data taking is piloted by the Run-Control window, visible in the centre of the picture. It sends commands to the two detector readout systems and processes the data through a set of producers and collectors. Green lines are used for command and synchronisation signals, yellow lines for configuration data, large blue, red and purple lines for SiW ECAL, AHCAL and common data, respectively.

4. ADAPTATION OF COMPACT SIW ECAL READOUT TO AHCAL

The basis of technical specifications for common DAQ interfaces is CALICE SiW ECAL SL-Board v2, described in Section 2. The experience gained during beam tests in 2021 and 2022 with 15 layers in operation, and use in small test bench setup in different locations (IJClab, LLR and Kyushu U.), gives confidence that this solution is technically mature for a transfer to other applications.

The current interface of each layer of CALICE AHCAL prototype consists of a Central Interface Board (CIB) carrying three mezzanines: one for the communication of the up-to 72 SPIROC2e ASICs, called Detector InterFace (DIF) board, one handling the power supply (POWER board), and one for the calibration (CALIB) board, driving the layer's LED calibration system. While this design enables a fast replacement of the individual mezzanines, which has proven to be very useful and reliable for many beam tests, it is not optimal in terms of compactness. The SiW ECAL example demonstrate that a significant reduction of the size of the interface boards, from their current size of $\sim 36 \times 10 \text{ cm}^2$, could be achieved.

However, the SiW ECAL and the AHCAL differ in several aspects, that have to be taken into account in the adaptation to the CALICE AHCAL. They have been identified as:

1. Integration of power pulsing on AHCAL Board: power pulsing is one of the key technologies for linear-collider detectors and is already implemented into the CALICE prototypes. In power-pulsing mode, the bias currents of the front-end electronics are periodically shut down following the beam structure of the collider. In case of the SiW ECAL, the power will be

stored locally, next to the ASICs, on the front-end boards, in the time interval between the bunch trains and released during the bunch trains. Therefore, the current flowing through the SL-Board is limited to 200 mA. For the AHCAL, the powering concept has been designed to keep components producing a significant amount of heat on the interfaces, where cooling is available. Therefore, the large capacitances storing the power as well as the regulators are located on the POWER board. With newer generations of SiPMs, that are less sensitive to temperature changes, it might be possible to lower the requirements on temperature changes and gradients within the AHCAL volume, and to implement a powering scheme similar to the SiW ECAL. On the other hand, one should take into account that the next generation of readout ASICs will be likely produced in a technology with lower input voltage (1.2 V instead of the 3.3 V powering the SKIROC2 [of SiW ECAL] and SPIROC2 [of AHCAL] ASICs). This would lead to a higher relative loss on the regulator. The effect of this should be investigated with a thermal simulation.

2. The AHCAL features a LED system for calibration purposes. Therefore, the control of the LED system would have to be integrated into the new compact readout.
3. The AHCAL power board provides the analog and digital supply voltages to the ASICs, the SiPM bias voltages and the LED bias voltage. The SiPM bias voltages can be adjusted for each channel with the SPIROC2e ASIC, but only in a limited range (from 2.5 V to 4.5 V, depending on the ASIC configuration). The SiPM bias voltage, supplied by the POWER board, is defined by the hardware configuration of the POWER board, with a fine adjustment by software in a range of roughly 4 V. In order to operate with various SiPM types that require different bias voltages, spanning over much more than 4 V, it is very useful to have the flexibility to exchange power boards easily. Therefore, it might be useful to keep the POWER board as a separate mezzanine.
4. For reasons of signal integrity, the length of the transmission lines cannot exceed much the length of the ones in the CORE Kapton of the SiW ECAL. Due to the larger dimensions of the HCAL, it is therefore not possible to use a Kapton cable. On the other hand, the channel density in the HCAL is lower, making more standard cables a possible solution. The AHCAL DAQ requires five differential line pairs per connection, limiting the choice of commercially available cables. At the moment, the AHCAL uses HDMI cables with standard HDMI connectors (type A) to the layer interfaces, and micro-HDMI connectors (type D) on the side facing the data concentration. A similar solution, maybe with smaller connectors (mini or micro-HDMI) also on the layer interface side, might also be employed for the compact readout system.
5. Currently, the AHCAL DIF contains a Zynq-7020 system-on-chip to handle the communication of the SPIROC ASICs in a layer, while the SiW ECAL SL-boards are based on the ALTERA MAX10 mixed CPLD/FPGA low power technology. It needs to be investigated if the functionality necessary for the AHCAL can be implemented on a MAX10.

5. A SPIN-OFF – CONTRIBUTION TO THE LUXE EXPERIMENT

The LUXE collaboration aims at studying the QED in extreme conditions by colliding medium energy (10–17 GeV) electron and photon beams with an intense laser beam. Non-linear Compton scattering and e^+e^- pair production should arise. Their detection requires highly-granular silicon-tungsten calorimeters as described here and compact forward calorimetry as developed by the FCAL collaborations [8].

As a possible spin-off of the work described before the compact DAQ and the common interface described here could be extended to work with one of the prototypes of the FCAL for the LUXE experiment, to start in 2025. Note in this context that TAU, one of the leading institutes in LUXE is also participant in the Task 8.1.

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
SiW ECAL	Silicon Tungsten Electromagnetic Calorimeter
AHCAL	Analogue Hadronic Calorimeter
ILD	International Large Detector